

BLUE COLLAR MARKET AND PROSPECTIVE ON GLOBAL LEVEL: WITH REFERENCE TO INDIAN BLUE MARKET

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1. ABSTRACT:-

Globalization led to supply chain of the skilled and non-skilled workers in Developing and non-developing countries, it improve economic conditions of the employees as well as it helps in increasing GDP. as per the report of International Labor Organization(ILO)in a every country five workers are employed on global supply chain .in the pandemic time of 2019/2020from the ILO and social report of different countries shows that employment generation capacity ,heavy production ,good transportation facility, standard amount of wages maintain global supply chain of the workers they get tempted for bright career .

As per the study of labor organization it is found the south Asian countries are producing best and cheap labor for global supply chain of labor, as per the foreign market and big foreign brands criticized labor market because they are facing social problems with the foreign workers, simultaneously many labor organizations and NGO's campaign the poor laborer's which are outsource companies have to provide best facilities for their survival, why in Covid-19 company stated that shutdown conditions, many automobile companies ,production industries and many more they start shut down conditions for the foreign labors and why they came back to their countries, somehow economic conditions and survival conditions were not up to the mark. But question is that how to adjust global label market, In the Indian context unrest conditions and economy compound are not well, globalization has fostered step competition in labor market with develop and developing countries.

Key words-Supply chain, Organization, Labor, ILO, Develop and Developing Countries.

2. INTRODUCTION:-

A few studies show the crises of the labor in skilled and non-skilled market last 20 years we can see globally every labor market facing this crisis. Many factors are involved in this crisis flow (1) mechanisms of labor market adjustment; (2) cyclicity of job flows(3) the extent to which these flows prove heterogeneous across firms and workers (4) whether employment adjustments lead to changes in employment structure. This crisis turns up in to the job crisis and unemployment. As per the report of International labor organization (ILO) every five workers have employed on globally labor market little but strongly they are producing economy. In today's scenario evidence proved that every countries labor policies are failed due to recession and it not promoting adjustment of the labor. Although globally every country facing this crisis but as per the Indian context Indian labor are very cheap and population on boom stage so that in India labors can easily available simultaneously globally Indian labor are easily approachable . In the UAE as per the data 22% labors are Indian who are engaged in small to large work.

In the context of India labor market is characterized by the different wages policies although Constitution of India has given full rights to the labors but due to uneducated they don't know their rights.

As per the report of 2020, in the India there were around 476.67 million workers in India, the second largest after China. Out of which, agriculture industry consist of 41.19%, industry sector consist of 26.18% and service sector consist 32.33% of total labor force.

According to the report of state of working India the majority of jobs created in India are in the informal sector, often leading to job insecurity, low wages and lack of labor protection. India will take 27 year more from the date and year to be biggest labor market in the global economy.

3. LITERATURE REVIEWS:-

In her research **Caselli, Mauro', (2021)** she examine globally that every fast growing and slow economy facing imperfection of labors, not in India but all over the world ,many countries are dependent on tourism economy and the workers who are engaged in Hotel industry are not educated and perfect but globally everywhere every country managing labor adjustment simultaneously we can find out somehow this adjustment increment potential and skills set with those labors who are unskilled Manufacturing industries in France are producing good labor market because they are providing quality up gradation .

In this research **Agarwal, Shakshi', and Chakraborty, Debashish', (2020)** it is found that in India During the last two decades, India has witnessed several trade and industrial policy reforms. It examine the relationship between dynamism of India's two-way trade, measured through Marginal Intra-Industry Trade (MIIT) labor market adjustments reflected through absolute employment changes, in select manufacturing sectors .Results indicate that MIIT increase in productivity, skilled workforce intensity, industrial concentration, incremental FDI inflows and trade openness positively influence absolute employment changes, whereas unskilled wage exerts a negative impact on the same .many offshore industries hire unskilled employees it balance there economy

In his Research article **Das, Keshav, (2017)** he explore this statement that crucial variable influencing labor market characteristics and behavior. Further, it critically reviews several important labor regulations in India in terms of their actual implementation and relevance in an informal sector driven industrial economy. Reflections on labor reforms in times of growing interface between Indian enterprises and global buyers have been made commenting on the functional dynamics of global production networks.

In his research paper **D'Souza, (2008)** he has extensively focused that labor market of the India as well as global level attracted the wages and other perks which must be essentially required for the survival. Very popular view of the integration of the new technology it has change the economical level of the market every super market on global level demand skilled workers but companies are not paying sufficient amount of the wages, legislations rules are different and it direct effect on demand and supply of the labor. Manufacturing industries are more reliable then the agriculture and its gives the financial support, in India as per the report 70% people are village residential and 15% people every year leaving their land because agriculture is not fixed economy it depends upon the environmental conditions, government rules are hard for the agriculturist so people are searching their future in cities and out of India. But due to legislature demand and supply on global level somehow difficult In his Research paper **Bottini , Novella, (2007)** he explore that before second world war off shoring outsource of the employees is very much fascinated object for the undeveloped countries

people because it was giving Global economy ,proper labor legislation and another benefits big organizations wee hiring cheap labors and it was maintain demand and supply rules.

4. Objectives of the study:-

1. To study the Labor Market Adjustment.
2. To study which factors impact on labor market.
3. To study which factors tempted to the labor
4. To study Government legislations about the labor.
5. To study the benefits of labor
6. To study the future growth of labor

5.ILO REPORT:-

The ILO report covers the internal and external affairs of the world political views which affect the labor market and demand and supply. It extent the consequences of the labor market disruption caused by the overlapping economy, geopolitical crisis heavy impact of religion .it direct effect on the labor market .as per the report it is found that many labors from the undeveloped countries are not going back to the foreign countries where from last from six month or many years they were busy to increasing GDP of working countries due to many reason specifically after covid-19. The report pays particular attention to the impact of the different crises on productivity, job quality and job opportunities and how these trends risk undermining social justice around the world.

The global wages report shows their report that wages conditions for the blue collar employees out the the countries is not well people who are engaged in work out of the countries survivals tuff arranging household food rent taxes and other expenses are very high rather than Demand of the Indian labor is on boom, Numbers of employees are not interested to go out of India. As the world economy started to recover from that crisis, by the global rise in inflation in the absence of adequate policy responses, the near future could see a sharp erosion of the real incomes of workers and their families and an increase in inequality, threatening the economic recovery and possibly fuelling further social unrest

This edition of the Global Wage Report shows that wages and the purchasing power of households have been dented considerably during the past three years, first by the COVID-19 pandemic and then, as the world economy started to recover from that crisis, by the global rise in inflation. Available evidence for 2022 suggests that rising inflation is causing real wage growth to dip into negative figures in many countries, reducing the purchasing power of the middle class and hitting low-income groups particularly hard. This cost-of living crisis comes on top of significant losses in the total wage bill for workers and their families during the COVID-19 crisis, which in many countries had the greatest impact on low-income groups. In the absence of adequate policy responses, the near future could see a sharp erosion of the real incomes of workers and their families and an increase in inequality, threatening the economic recovery and possibly fuelling further social unrest.

6. GDP CONTRIBUTION OF INDIAN LABOR IN INDIAN ECONOMY:-

India will grow to become the world`s third largest economy in 2027.

Labor in India refers to employment in the economy of India. In 2020, there were around 476.67 million workers in India, the second largest after China. Out of which, agriculture

industry consist of 41.19%, industry sector consist of 26.18% and service sector consist 32.33% of total labor force. Of these over 94 percent work in unincorporated, unorganized enterprises ranging from pushcart vendors to home-based diamond and gem polishing operations. The organized sector includes workers employed by the government, state-owned enterprises and private sector enterprises. In 2008, the organized sector employed 27.5 million workers, of which 17.3 million worked for government or government owned entities. India's GDP is expected to rise from \$2.7 trillion in 2019 to \$5 trillion in 2025 and \$8.4 trillion in 2030, according to a Bloomberg Economic article and its projections.

India is a big country last from 10years many of the industrialists from the world economy are taking interest to invest money in Indian market because Indian labor is very hard working and result oriented

India s GDP basically depends up on the Tertiary sector mainly deals with the services service sector in the Indian economy contribute in large amount of GDP.

17, 48,000 register industries are in the India those small and big industries are contributing huge amount of GDP

Three sectors model have divide in the Indian economy that is extraction of raw materials (primary), manufacturing (secondary), and service industries which exist to facilitate the transport, distribution and sale of goods produced in the secondary sector (tertiary).

Indian labor market contributing 6% to 6.8 % GDP to Indian economy, its huge contribution of the three sectors which are existing in India

As per the economy survey and contribution of primary, Secondary and Tertiary sector will contribute 8% full GDP in 2030⁽¹⁾

This is the statement by the government of India that if more women's will join all three sectors India can manage 8% GDP growth by 2030⁽²⁾

India's booming service industry is a remarkable illustration of how modern economic growth models can outperform traditionally established ones. India has the fastest-growing service sector which is contributing over 50% to the country's GDP⁽³⁾

Indian labor market is very strong and by three sectors of economy producing good GDP for the country surly it will increase future of economy. Although many factors are included in this

7. SKILLS DEVELOPMENT (DREAM OF INDIA'S PRIME MINISTER (2024):-

India's Prime Minister Honourable MR. Narendra Modi Sir urged chief secretaries of the state's to put thrust to develop human skills and entrepreneurship of shining India a dream for 2047 by 07th January 2024 in new Delhi, He focused that every state have to make a broad policies for the young entrepreneurs he said its mandatory for India's GDP skilled labour can adjust demand supply rule in India because in coming years India will be first world power of the

Prime Minister NarendraModi sir asserted that India will be a developed country by 2047. Addressing the country during the 77th Independence, the Prime Minister declared that by 2047, the year marking India's 100th year of independence, the nation would achieve developed country status. Concept of skills development talks about the involvement of the young energy in Indian economy. as concept talk about the literate and skilled oriented employees and labours can make India and globe happy. Skilled labour can adjust the labour market demand world is going turn on technology and India is playing vital role in it. Skill

development talk about the formers, fisherman, small scale industry, women's agriculturist lower wages receiver labours. Skilled India will be top in the world and other countries will depend upon India's labour. Government of India is making ground level legislation for the labours and every year blue collar employees generate 1.25% GDP of the India.

8. GROUND REALITY (HOW TO DEVELOP SKILL DEVELOPMENT):-

The importance of skill development in India has been cited as one of the most important factor in job creation. Skills and knowledge are the driving forces of economic growth and social development for any country, Nowadays everyone aspires to have a successful career,

National Skill Development Mission The National Skill Development Mission was launched by the Hon'ble Prime Minister on 15th July, 2015 on the occasion of World Youth Skills Day. It aims to create convergence and expedite cross-sartorial decisions through a high powered decision making framework. It is expected to converge, coordinate, implement and monitor skilling activities on a pan-India basis

The objective of Skill Development is to create a workforce empowered with the necessary and continuously upgraded skills, knowledge and internationally recognized qualifications to gain access to decent employment and ensure Although the government has put in place a number of plans for skill development, these plans have not yielded the desired results in terms of creating opportunities for skill development training in India.* Increasing proficiency* Expanding skill sets* Completing tasks in a shorter amount of time with more outcomes* Increasing performance level

9. MIGRATION OF INDIAN EMPLOYEES, A GLOBAL REPORT:-

In the present time India is the biggest country in the world where migration rate of the Indian are very high. Presently 1.75 carorers Indian are living on different area of the world who are producing good economy although 80% employees are poor, as per the American report maximum Indians are working in developed countries and they are full filling the labour adjustment on different stages, migrate Indian are sending money in dollars in Indian banks which are increasing Indian rupees value in international market. globally it is tough to adjust the labour demand from India but Indian are doing best simultaneously they are facing many problems which is the biggest gap to adjust labour demand on international level like

- (1) Recruitment problem
- (2) labour sailing because they are not aware by legal laws. 80% employees are semi-skilled and illiterate and they are blue collar employees who are working in America, Dubai, Japan, China,, Germany and many countries, specially they migrate from home town to foreign for earning well but in the developed countries they tempted by the good life style and good earning, somehow we can say they trapped by good financial structure. Actually financial condition of India is not up to the mark that is why many people are leaving home states for earning.

10. GOOD GOVERNANCE SYSTEM IN INDIA AND ITS IMPACT ON LABOR ADJUSTMENT:-

प्रजासुखेसुखंराजःप्रजानांचहितेहितम्।नात्मप्रियंप्रियंराजःप्रजानांतुप्रियंप्रियम्॥

Good governance refers to the effective and efficient management of a country and state. Participation, accountability, transparency, effectiveness and efficiency, equitable and inclusive, consensus-oriented, strategic approach, and rule of law, are widely recognized as the hallmarks of good governance at the national and international level.

India is a Sovereign Socialist Secular Democratic Republic with a Parliamentary form of government which is federal in structure with unitary features at national level. This system should be such that one can give one's best, To serve and do good to the people, solving problems and their life To make life livable, content and joyful Be inspired by the desire of

Good governance defined as taking administrative decisions for smooth running the conditions for the people, administrative and for the employees, in the year 1992 world bank has decided the appropriate definition of good governance is the 'Governance and Development' by this it is decided that government will take decision for country development which will increase the economy and social structure of the country, the social structure will be sound we can see the impact on demand and supply rules.

11. LABOUR LAWS FOR THE BLUE COLLAR EMPLOYEES IN INDIAN CONTEXT:-

The Indian workforce is the largest in the world, with more than 500 million workers. India has a complex employment law system that is governed by various government bodies and agencies. These laws are meant to protect both the employee and the employer and ensure that their rights are respected. There are certain laws that apply only to certain work environments, and there are some that apply universally. Most of these labour laws govern blue-collar workers (i.e., workers), whereas white-collar employees' employment terms are largely governed by private contracts. Labour laws are a set of compliances that set the tone for the treatment of the labour force in the workplace. Labour is the greatest asset for an organisation and to ensure that their rights are protected and to safeguard them against any exploitation, labour laws are enforced. Labour Laws are imposed by both State as well as Central Governments.

India is a very wide country and spread there legal branches everywhere specially where constitution can save legal rights of human. In the labor constitution Article 21 and Article 19 is very essential for the blue color employees.

The right to livelihood is an essential component of the right to life under Article 21. The Supreme Court has held that the right to livelihood includes the right to work and earn a livelihood, and the government cannot deprive a person of his/her livelihood without following the due process of law.

Labour Policy of India Labour policy in India has been evolving in response to specific needs of the situation to suit requirements of planned economic development and social justice and has two fold objectives, namely maintaining industrial peace and promoting the welfare of labour.

The government of India recently consolidated 29 different laws into four main codes to simplify its federal labour laws, The wages code, The industrial relations code, The occupational safety, Health and working conditions code and the social security code

The central government has proposed to replace 29 existing labor laws with four codes. Its objective is to simplify and modernize labor regulation.

The major challenge in labor reforms is to facilitate employment growth while protecting the rights of workers.

Purpose of labour legislation

Labour legislation that is adapted to the economic and social challenges of the modern world of work fulfils three crucial roles (1) it establishes a legal system that facilitates productive

individual and collective employment relationships, and therefore a productive economy, (2) it establishes a legal system that facilitates productive individual and collective employment relationships, and therefore a productive economy,(3) providing a framework within which employers, workers and their representatives can interact with regard to work-related issues, it serves as an important vehicle for achieving harmonious industrial relations based on workplace democracy.

12. CSR-CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY AND LABOR WELFARE:-

Corporate Social Responsibility has become a compulsory act under section 135 of the Companies Act, 2013 but it fails to include any kind of directions related to labour laws and the rights of the work force. This paper talk about analysis the current situation of the CSR laws in India in an attempt to draw attention to the lack of representation of the weak labour class which is an important part of the society but is conveniently ignored in the aforementioned act. CSR should supplement the labour laws present in the country to make the system better as only a formal and legal recognition of the same can bring any relevant change to the current unfortunate state of the labour markets in India. The Companies Act, 2013, Corporate Social Responsibility is now a mandatory act to be followed as per the official notification dated 27th February 2014. According to the Section 135 of the act, following corporate social responsibility is now a compulsion for all companies. Corporate social responsibility, also called corporate citizenship, companies can be conscious of the kind of impact they are having on all aspects of society, including economic, social, and environmental. We feel that the current legislation for the CSR of the companies needs to address the issue of labour welfare rights which is effective in protecting the interests of the stakeholders of the company. Therefore, there is an immediate need to include the stakeholders and the workers' participation in making the code of conduct and other CSR tools instead of making a unilateral decision from the management. In the European countries, there are participants of the workers and other stakeholders in the drafting and implementation of codes of conduct. An important recommendation related to CSR is provided by the International Labour Organization, which is the inclusion of protection for Freedom of Association (FoA) and Right to Collective Bargain (CB) in the CSR charter of the companies. ILO's recommend to every organization to focus on domestic wages work hours, child labour, and discrimination. CSR in India is a relatively new concept that is still in the process of development as time passes. Companies in India actively engage in CSR activities due to the law passed in India. A study conducted in 2008 by TNS India and Times Foundation, showed that over 90% of all major Indian organizations surveyed were involved in CSR activities with the private companies being more active in the CSR activities than the governmental organizations. However, as stated above, CSR in India has a very narrow understanding of the concept it has become more donor-driven than local in approach to unilateral decision making. Owing to the lack of clear-cut guidelines or policy directives CSR activities have become initiatives that a company engages in on basis of its size and profile the bigger the company is, the bigger its CSR projects are. Therefore, what India needs is an alternative framework that not only includes the proposed rights in the CSR activities but also Provides a guideline for the companies to engage in the CSR activities. Company engages in on basis of its size and profile, the bigger the company is, the bigger its CSR projects are. Therefore what India needs is an alternative framework that not only includes the proposed rights in the CSR activities but also provides a guideline for the companies to engage in the CSR activities.\

13. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

There are some important limitations associated with this study. we recognize that the nature of the survey provided some constraints. Respondents were presented with force choice format which has been noted to cause methodological concern when preference uncertainty is present. in addition ,using a 5 –point Likert Type Scale with a neutral or fence sitting position options can distort preference when ambivalent feelings exist about the questions and item. This study is based on the labour demand and labour adjustment on global level it is very useful to know about the real labour graph in Indian context compare to any other context.

Future research is also needed to understand the role of the government to play a satisfactory role for the blue collar employees. This is especially important when discussing satisfaction and dissatisfaction that is achieved by the employees. in this study were divide in many parts but academic review of literature future qualitative research might need to be undertaken to further refine these dimensions' hope in future this study will fulfil understand labour market in Indian context.

CONCLUSION:-

Labor market adjustment on global level with special reference to Indian context-as we know it very well that before the independence of India 1947 it was a dumb and deaf country where survival of the fittest concept was taking shape with the few area of of the population it was the dark time for the Indian economy as well as the residential people of the India .we can find out our previous history where living hood were the sacristy in the country.

Gradually politically stability and constitution came in the force and thing were going well specially for the labors when labor law act came in the action.

Glorious outcome of the globalization are the phenomenal in every countries GDP. growth of the developed and developing countries like Good infrastructure big shopping malls. Six to four lens roads, high speed trains, good local transportations and many more.

It is found that in metro cities job opportunities from higher to lower level are in good quantity it's filling the number of unemployment, unskilled employee gets average labor wages and gradually he/she converts their skills as expert worker. Even they shift their families in cities. Other side of the global market it is find out that Indian labors very cheap then other countries so that many of the developed countries they hire the Indian labor as provide best labor jobs it is satisfactory of their families. Newly elected government are taking interest in labor market and providing best facilities to their families such as grocery, medical facilities, education, Gas, houses and many more. Its positive change in labor market of the India,

World's Economy outsources Indian labor for their supporting jobs out of the India. Home based workers are mostly remaining out of the purview of global buyers. it is true that India has bigger chunk of the home workers. Few conditions are very alarming for the country policy makers have to focus on that. Despite of this the survey Cleary shows that India has to improve their concern for the labor. Foreign and domestic policy makers have to find out micro and macro factors which are affecting the labor adjustment in Indian level. Although India is a signatory to work agenda of ILO and this mandate will have top embedded in all in policies.

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